

Engaging Gen Z through social media marketing.

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Abstract

Generation Z, is a generation that has grown up with the internet and social media, and which is now between mid 1990s to early 2010s. The ability to market to this generation through S. M. M. has become important for those brands seeking to continue appealing to customers in this generation. Due to this, the present research seeks to analyze the current social media usage of Gen Z in terms of their use of brands on social media platforms, contents and the utilization of influencer marketing. An online quantitative survey with 48 participants was used to measure how much time young people use social media, which platforms they use, how much they trust influencer recommendations and what type of content engages them with brands. According to the study, 71% of Gen Z cares about the ethical position of brands; 61% choose fun or informative content; and 72% tend to interact more with the influencer's they deem sincere. Furthermore, it also exposed short videos, heavy text posts as becoming important reasons among participants for unfollowing brands. The results of this study are beneficial for the brands that are aiming at achieving the best results from the interaction with the fully mobilized generation of Gen Z on social networks, by providing recommendations on the creation of topic-based, engagement-focused, and value-based content, as well as the use of influencer marketing that will be synergistic with the expectations of this generation.

Keywords: Generation Z, social media marketing,

1.Introduction

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In today's world, social media has turned into an indispensable platform for brands to connect with their targeted customers, and there is no one more connected with social media than the Gen Z population whose families are pinning, liking and creating accounts across Tiktok, Instagram, YouTube, and so on since the mid-1990s to early 2010s. Since the buy power of Gen Z is still massive and growing, it is important for companies that hope to remain relevant in the marketplace to consider how they can follow social influencers to capture their attention and sell their products.

From this, it is clear that Gen Z is unique in consume content and the way it is consumed because the world owes Gen Z experiences which are real, relatable, and creative. This is especially so when the brands are visually striking and avoid brands that are significantly

dissimilar to their personal values and character; brands with engaging, interactive, immersive campaigns. Therefore, conventional methods of ads are no longer very effective hence the need to make ad appeals to be dynamic and more of a customized approach that can engage the consumer with the product. In this article we discuss peculiarities of Gen Z and reveal the key aspects of Social Media Marketing activation to such audience.

2. Literature Review

Social Media Impact: Gen z and Millenial on the Cathedra of Social Media, Richa Gupta opine that through social media marketing has become one of the effective ways of reaching out to the Millennials, who form a generation that was born and raised using social media The current research shows that millennials using social media marketing is more effective as compared to other generations. However, creating a social media presence by itself cannot be considered as social media marketing; it involves knowing how to use the social media to communicate with the consumers through contents which will be appealing to them (Tuten and Solomon, 2017). The lack of perceived authenticity and a failure to target individual consumers has been cited as being detrimental to social media marketing among the Millennial generation as has the lack of interactivity apparent in many social media campaigns. While this remains a reality, more and more brands are realizing the training attributes associated with social networking sites in influences consumer awareness and brand preference.

2.1 Digital Marketing Strategies: Effectiveness on Generation Z.

In Anjum, Asma and Thomas, Mary Rani's estimation, digital marketing approaches are necessary for new generation Z, a ubiquitous generation that uses digital platforms and social media extensively. It is discovered that this generation can well access, accommodate and appreciate digital content that are relevant, engaging, participative and real, thus bottling marketers' traditional techniques into suits these preferences Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) are useful in making the most appropriate digital marketing strategies and ensure that they align to the characters and characteristics of Generation Z. Previous research has focused on increasing the reliability of digital marketing components in order to come up with relevant and highly focused effective measures and techniques of communication for Gen Z This paper contributes to the knowledge domain by providing marketers with a framework for designing best-fit data-driven digital marketing communication strategies for Gen Z. (Artemova, 2018)

2.2 Teaching Generation Z social media marketing: A micro-influencer project.

For this reason, influencer marketing has turned into one of the essential approaches brands use to engage the contemporary consumer, let alone Gen Z, who freely spend time on social media. Misel have found out that micro influencer; people who have a smaller number of followers but are very interactive to them, can make a big difference in the creation of brand consciousness and customer trust The approach of using students as micro influencers is one that is adapted in practice where students are exposed to the different strategies used in social media but in a manner that will encourage reflection. In prior research, it is shown that doing assignments in the subject of digital marketing is valuable as the attendance to social media platforms enables the students to gain hands-on experience in the matter. This work presents a useful source of information

regarding the operational use of social media marketing and underlines the importance of such a experience for the members of the Generation Z students. (Mandagi and Aseng, 2021)

3.Problem Statement

The consumers of Gen Z have become an important consumer segment and therefore understanding their behaviours and especially on social media can be an advantageous for brands targeting to capture this group of consumers. Although these marketing strategies can be ineffective for this generation of consumers, knowing the characteristics of social network sites as well as the engagement behavior of Gen Z is critical to the success of a business. Still now the social networks are becoming more and more popular as the marketing tool, the brands fail to produce content that actually attend the Gen Z audience and encourages them to be loyal to the specific brand or to make purchases. The objective of this article will be to review what has been established regarding engagement of Gen Z on social media and identify the approaches which will make more sense to brands as they seek to create meaningful relations with this generation. (Sayyed and Gupta, 2020)

4.Research Questions

The research was guided by the following questions to effectively achieve its intended goals:

1. In what ways does the Gen Z audience share the various kinds of content on the social platforms?
2. In what way do Gen Z perceive the various influencers and what influence do these influencers have on them in terms of brand decisions?
3. From the next section on the case company, what features of brands can generate Gen Z's attention on social media?

5.Purpose of the Study

This work focuses on understanding how to market to Gen Z through social media marketing to equip businesses and marketers with more insight and knowledge of how this generation relates, their choices, and their perception to social media content. As they are counted among the most conscious generations of customers, the GenZ has different expectations and perceptions of marketing wrapped in social media platforms.

6. Research Methods

This research aims at finding out the experience of Generation Z on brand social media marketing. Semi structured questionnaires were administered to them in order to get information on their frequency of use in social media sites, their preferred sites, and their perception on engaging brands on the sites. The survey was completed by 48 subjects who all belong to the Generation Z with aged between 18 to 23 years. The reason for directing the survey at this age group is that it is the most active age group primarily targeting social networking sites. The survey aimed to examine several key areas: Their participation on social media, the number of hours young generation use social media per day, on which social media platform, the extent to which they interact with brand content, their level of trust with endorsing influencers, reasons of following or unfollowing brands, etc. Through the assessment of the responses this study seeks to capture the attitudes and actions of this Generation Y –the digitally aware generation so that brands interested in engaging this generation on social media can do so effectively. (Jabr, 2022)

7.Findings

Analyzing the results of the survey shown below will provide several profound insights concerning the social media preferences of Gen Z. The age distribution of the respondents was as follows: 18 to 20 years, 70.8% which means the survey captured mainly the young generation Z

Based on the time spent on social media, 43.8% of the participants use 3 to 4 hours per day on social media platform 33.3% uses 1 to 2 hours. A slightly higher 12,5% spends less than an hour and 10,4% spend over 5 hours in social media usage. This means that social media is integrated in the everyday use of gen Z and a popular part of the population engages in multiple hours of social media usage.

54.2% of respondents said they actively use telegram as a social media platform and 37.5% use Instagram often. Other platforms included YouTube at 8.3% and Facebook attractively at 0% preferred by this age group. This means that more of Gen Z use new generation platforms that

include real-time messaging features and multimedia content like Telegram and Instagram as opposed to normal platforms such as Facebook.

Regarding the content of advertisements that were post within the social media platforms, 35.4% of respondents said the preferred amusing or entertaining videos, 27.1% preferred educative or ‘how to’ videos while 22.9 % stated their preference was with influencer reviews and only 14.6% preferred product promotions or discounts. This means that Gen Z is much more receptive to humorous or informative content rather than product communications in the traditional ad sense.

Survey also showed that 52.1% of respondent depends on the specific product trust the influencer endorsements and 35.4% trust the influencers in general; whereas 12.5% do not trust the influencers at all while making a purchase. This infers that even though influencer marketing is effective it has its effectiveness governed by the kind of influencer as well as the kind of product is being marketed.

This proved understanding the motivational factors for following brands on social media where respondents responded with 50% on the basis of brand values/ethics, while another 22.9%

gave their following as due to exclusive offers/promotions. At the same time, 20,8% of the brands recognize their interest in influencer partnerships, while the same brands are more sceptical about involving social media challenges or live broadcasts and streams: only 6,3% of the brands are interested in such elements.

Looking at interactions with brand content, 37,5% seldom interact, 29,2% interact sometimes and 25% often. This indicates that although part of the Gen Z does engage with brand content, it is not as often or naturally as it would be expected.

Finally, about the factors that would make them to stop following a brand on the platform, 41,7% said that short videos (TikToks, Reels), while 20,8% said text-based posts and 18,8% said stories and live streams. This indicates that Gen Z can be overwhelmed by the overuse of some formats, or with the content ordering not appealing to them may stop paying much attention to brands which heavily use such formats.

8. Discussion

The established facts from this research give a clear picture of gen z participation in brand related social media interactions and influences. This is most evidenced by a highly compelling 85% affirmative response given by the Gen Z sample when asked whether brand values and ethics play a role in their decision to follow a brand on social media. This is supported by a growing awareness of the younger population of being more conscious with the kind of brands they associate with due to the companies' humanitarian and fungibility standards. Thus, the brands which declare the policy of Sustainability, Diversity, and ethical policies of their companies will get the devotion of Gen Z consumers. The survey also confirms a positive impact of influencer

advertising, especially if the influencer supports the product and the advertised brand. This is not to say that everyone trusts influencers, as 52.1% of respondents said their trust in influencers varies with the type of product being endorsed. This underlines the importance of brands' selection of influencers, with whom the brand's consumers are familiar and who they trust. Also, the shift from generic humorous and informative commercials to actual narratives describes the way that generation Z focuses with significance and engagement. For this reason, instead of aggressively marketing products, brands should seek to establish forms of content that can be perceived as entertaining, informative or valuable by this audience. It is also important to avoid making post purely for sales pitches as the audience would be most receptive to videos, how-To posts. The survey also shows that with the frequency of short videos (TikToks, Reels) and posts in the texture format, such as captions, being the main reasons people unfollow a brand, it can be concluded that Gen Z might find such formats too annoying and boring, or simply not engaging enough. Hence, brands mustn't overly rely on such formats but rather pay attention to the quality of the content shared and the general feel and purpose it serves to the viewer.

9. Conclusion

In this study, the author has presented useful information as to how the Gen Z population uses the social media platforms. With the help of the obtained results, it is possible to identify that, as in the previous analysis, brand values and ethics matter for the engagement of this generation with brands. Further, influencer marketing still proves powerful; however, it can only work if influencers are considered credible and within the line of the product. The fact that Gen Z prefer entertaining and informative content endorsements consequently means that labs need to offer value through entertainment and pass on information rather than product sells. Also, the ease of Gen Z to unfollow brands based on content format, especially short videos and text content mean that there is the need to choose the right content approach in order to avoid this. Brands interested in engaging Gen Z consumers should target their marketing communications as to the values, use effective and engaging content, and collaborate with proper influencers. With these strategies, it becomes easier for brands to appeal and sort for the attention of Gen Z and have sound cordial and loyal relationship depending on the results set by the brands.

Reference list

- Artemova, A. (2018). Alexandra Artemova ENGAGING GENERATION Z THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING Case: Hurja Media Oy. [online] Available at: https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/142658/Artemova_Alexandra.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y.
- Jabr, F. (2022). John A. Long - Publications List. Publicationslist.org, 14(6).
- Koval, R. (2016). Agents of Social Change: A Model for Targeting And Engaging Generation Z across Platforms: How a Nonprofit Rebuilt an Advertising Campaign To Curb Smoking by Teens and Young Adults. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 56(4), pp.414–425. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2501/jar-2016-046>.
- Mandagi, D. and Aseng, A. (2021). Millennials and Gen Z's Perception of Social Media Marketing Effectiveness on the Festival's Branding: The Mediating Effect of Brand Gestalt. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, [online] 21(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.59588/2350-8329.1389>.
- Razak, I. (2022). The Role of Digital Marketing for Generation Z. *Jurnal Ekonomi, Akuntansi dan manajemen Indonesia*, [online] 1(01), pp.18–25. Available at: <https://jurnal.seaninstitute.or.id/index.php/Juemi/article/view/512> [Accessed 22 Dec. 2024].

Sayyed, B.J.W. and Gupta, R. (2020). Social Media Impact: Generation Z and Millennial on the Cathedra of Social Media. [online] IEEE Xplore. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRITO48877.2020.9197995>.

Vallone, D., Smith, A., Kenney, T., Greenberg, M., Hair, E., Cantrell, J., Rath, J. and Koval, R. (2016). Agents of Social Change: A Model for Targeting And Engaging Generation Z across Platforms: How a Nonprofit Rebuilt an Advertising Campaign To Curb Smoking by Teens and Young Adults. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 56(4), pp.414–425. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2501/jar-2016-046>.

